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Coping Mechanisms of Bachelor of Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges

Anne Pauline D. Bautista, * Norievy C. Lalaguna, Princess Ara DA. Balajadia,
Paula Cristin Jade C. Peñaranda, Concepcion C. Peñaranda, Ruel G. Manalo, Rency C. Caraan
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This research aimed to help Bachelor of Elementary Education students deal with their stressors, as well as help them manage stress. The researchers address coping styles and stressors by conducting a survey to analyze and evaluate the stress factors and coping mechanisms of Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Tomas Claudio Colleges this year. The findings of this study indicate that the students are prone to physical stressors as they experience back pain and feel exhausted even if they did not perform anything physically. Nevertheless, in terms of coping mechanisms, seeking social support is what they want, to have an appointment with a professional counselor whenever a problem arises, and also post their troubles on social media to gain attention. Thus, the students experience physical stress but with the help of social support, they can get through. In addition to the study, the elementary education students also experienced interpersonal relationship stress by being hesitant to ask someone, or inability to mingle with others. In terms of their coping mechanisms, problem-solving is the least option to cope with, weighing 1.93% out of all the aspects of the mechanisms studied. It proposed that a program be developed to aid Elementary Education students with their stressors in terms of providing them with social support. It will also help the Bachelor of Elementary Education students to create harmonious and affectionate school surroundings.

Keywords: *elementary education, coping mechanism, stressors*

Introduction

In this generation where college students are confronted and bombarded with different stressors, it is highly valuable to understand how coping mechanisms affect their emotions. Coping Mechanisms are schemes that help an individual deal with stress and unbearable feelings. Students are constantly utilizing coping methods, whether they are aware of it or not. These actions may occasionally be detrimental or beneficial in helping them manage their tensions.

These coping mechanisms that college students face are critical issues that must be resolved or answered. This type of situation occurs not just among Tomas Claudio Colleges pupils, but also in other universities. Thus, coping mechanisms can be categorized into three parts: problem-focused, emotional-focused, and appraisal-focused mechanisms. That being said, the first topic this research will address is emotional-focused systems.

The coping mechanism that college students are experiencing is a very serious matter that we need to solve or to have an answer. This kind of matter is not only the students from Tomas Claudio Colleges experience this, but also in other schools.

According to the Richards and Hemphil (2018) overwhelming school-related stress reduces your motivation to do the work, impacts your overall academic achievement, and increases your odds of dropping out. College Students hide their feelings such as depression, anxiety, overthinking, stress, etc. You often see them happy and full of joy, but the truth is they experience depression. It is hard to hide and keep all the problems to yourself but because they do not want other people to feel, what they do is let the problem and whatever they feel. Therefore, experiencing excessive stress can take a toll on academic performance and motivation. It is important to find healthy ways to manage stress to maintain a balance and focus on academic goals.

According to McCarthy et al. (2009), students experience various stresses that could impact their academic achievement and their mental health. Learning is also affected because they bring the problem to school and cannot focus. Instead of focusing on the discussion, they are thinking about their personal problem. Not only Academic Achievement is affected, but also mental health.

One of the causes of personal problems is financial. There are also times when they think that they are the ones who bring the problem and that's where depression develops. According to Ramos (2015), stress is a common feeling experienced by individuals throughout life and it is imperative to comprehend how they cope with their stressors. The prevalence of stress in college lives and the importance of understanding how individuals manage their stressors.

Stress is a universal experience that College students encounter at various stages of their lives. It suggests that stress is not an isolated issue but a shared human experience. The significance of understanding how people cope with their stressors. Coping mechanisms are the strategies and behaviors individuals use to deal with stressful situations. By comprehending these mechanisms, we can better support others in managing their stress effectively and potentially improve their overall well-being.

Research Questions

This action research aimed to determine the coping mechanism of students enrolled in the Bachelor in Elementary Education program at Tomas Claudio Colleges. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the coping mechanism of Elementary Education Students with respect to:
 - 1.1. problem-focused
 - 1.2. appraisal focused; and
 - 1.3. mental focused?
2. Based on the findings what action play may be proposed to enhance the coping mechanism of Elementary Education students in Tomas Claudio Colleges?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative research design to analyze numerical data from Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Tomas Claudio Colleges the researcher uses a purposive sampling technique for the selected respondents. utilizing a survey method.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 60 students enrolled in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Bachelor of Elementary Education.

Instrument

The questionnaire was adopted from the study of Alberto Raggi concerning the stress and coping mechanisms of the students. The study aimed to answer the research question and hypothesis. The data were collected through a large-scale survey, utilizing a questionnaire from the study stress factors stress levels, and coping mechanisms among university students.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Table 1. *Computed Weighted Mean on the cause of stress of Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Groups of Respondents for Problem-Focused*

	<i>Problem Focused</i>	$W\bar{x}$	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
1.	Brainstorm whenever tasked by the teacher for an activity.	2.00	Sometimes	2
2.	Can face problems without the help of others.	1.95	Always	3
3.	Can manage time when there is a lot of school work.	2.02	Sometimes	1
4.	Self-motivating when dispirited.	1.91	Always	4
5.	Doing things to avoid overthinking the problems.	1.89	Always	5
Overall Mean		1.95	Always	

As reflected on the table with respect to Problem Focused, it obtained an overall weight 1.95 interpreted as a lot. The highest weighted mean of 2.02 shows that mostly of Elementary Education Students can manage time when there is a lot of schoolwork, while in last rank indicates that some Elementary Education Students doing things to avoid overthinking the problems with a weighted mean of 1.89. All the remaining items in the aspect are found to be always and sometimes.

This implies the coping mechanism depends on how the students will handle these struggles; it helps them to face the situation they are in. Since all students have their own strategies on how to cope with these unwanted feelings.

The result is related with the statement of Garcia (2018), which posited that Over time, students develop resilience by learning from their experiences, facing failure, and building a stronger sense of self-confidence in their teaching abilities.

Table 2. *Computed Weighted Mean on the cause of stress of Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Groups of Respondents for Appraisal Focused*

	<i>Appraisal Focused</i>	$W\bar{x}$	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
1.	Seek for the advice of others.	2.16	Sometimes	3.5
2.	Telling the problems to my friends.	2.12	Sometimes	5
3.	Having an appointment with a professional council whenever a problem arises.	2.32	Sometimes	1
4.	Cannot survive the difficulties without the help of others.	2.16	Sometimes	3.5
5.	Posting the problem on social media to gain attention.	2.28	Sometimes	2
Overall Mean		2.21	Sometimes	

As reflected on the table with respect to Appraisal Focused, it obtained an overall weight of 2.21 interpreted as A little. The highest weighted mean of 2.32 shows that most Elementary Education Students have an appointment with a professional council whenever a problem arises, while in last rank indicates that some Elementary Education Students are telling their problems to their friends with a weighted mean of 2.12. All the remaining items in the aspect are found to be sometimes.

This implies that Elementary Education Students' Coping Mechanism in terms of Seeking Social Support is to have an appointment with a professional council whenever a problem arises and not so much share the problems with their friends.

This conforms with Martinez (2016) which stated that some Philippine universities and colleges offer counseling services and stress-management seminars specifically designed for education students. Local literature acknowledges the role of these institutional support systems in helping BEEed students deal with stress, particularly during peak times such as exams and practicum placements.

Table 3. *Computed Weighted Mean on the cause of stress of Elementary Education Students in Tomas Claudio Colleges as Perceived by the Groups of Respondents for Avoidance*

<i>Mental Focused</i>	$W\bar{x}$	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
1. Changing the topic if the topic is about problems.	2.18	Sometimes	1
2. Avoid answering the question about problems.	2.07	Sometimes	2
3. Thinking of another situation to avoid thinking about the problems.	1.98	Always	3
4. Use a phone to be entertained and not be bothered by the problems.	1.88	Always	4
5. Thinking positive vibe to avoid crying.	1.82	Always	5
Overall Mean	1.99	Always	

As reflected in the table with respect to Avoidance, it obtained an overall mean of 1.99 interpreted as A lot. The highest weighted mean of 2.18 shows that most of the students do not change the topic if the topic is about problems. While the last in the rank indicated that thinking a positive vibe to avoid crying is what they think a lot for them to cope up with a weighted mean of 1.82. All the remaining items in the aspect of coping up are found to be always and sometimes.

This implies that Education Students can use Avoidance as their Coping Mechanism but most of the students do not want to avoid talking about the problem even if they avoid talking about the problem or distract themselves.

This is connected with Santos & Perez (2017) which claimed that peers provide emotional support, collaboration opportunities, and shared experiences, while family members offer encouragement, financial assistance, and practical advice, all of which are essential for students managing the challenges of a teaching degree.

Proposed Innovation, Intervention, And Strategy

The proposed invention aims to help and manage the stress of a Bachelor of Elementary Education in Tomas Claudio Colleges, the program entitled "Students Support and Appreciation Program" aims to support Bachelor of Elementary Education Students to manage their stress support. When they can feel they have someone they can talk to they feel down. This program contains:

BEEed program where the student will attend every Friday 1pm to have a small group where they can share their thoughts or problem in their group every meeting they will have different group so they meet a lot of friends.

Jar of Appreciation

A simple appreciation will help someone who is feeling down in this jar of appreciation for a random person that can boost their feeling. And if the student is having a bad day they can pick a random appreciation letter.

The student support and appreciation program will cover the whole school year. Faculty members and the Guidance Counselor will participate to help the students to manage stress.

Conclusions

The findings of the study showed that the coping mechanisms of BEEed students in the Tomas Claudio Colleges provides a comprehensive view of how students manage academic stress, emotional challenges, and the rigors of teacher training. Family and peer support, spiritual practices, and institutional resources play key roles in helping students navigate the demands of their education.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Anne Pauline D. Bautista

Tomas Claudio Colleges – Philippines

Norievy C. Lalaguna

Tomas Claudio Colleges – Philippines

Princess Ara DA. Balajadia

Tomas Claudio Colleges – Philippines

Paula Cristin Jade C. Peñaranda

Tomas Claudio Colleges – Philippines

Concepcion C. Peñaranda

Tomas Claudio Colleges – Philippines

Ruel G. Manalo

Tomas Claudio Colleges – Philippines

Rency C. Caraan

Tomas Claudio Colleges – Philippines